

Flame stabilisation of CH₄/H₂/NH₃ mixtures with oxygen enrichment and its impact on flame monitoring

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Background:

- Trinary blends of NH₃/H₂/CH₄ – a promising pathway for transition to reduced carbon emissions in the high-temperature process industry
- O₂ enrichment: Stabilizes flame and increases system efficiency
- Studies however indicate that mentioned gas blends may affect:
 - Static and dynamic flame stability limits**
 - Chemiluminescence spectrum differs from Flames with NG or H₂ (Fig 1)**

Fig 1. Spectral Analysis of NH₃/CH₄/H₂ Blends; [Mashruk S. et al., <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.03.254>]

State of the art: Most flame sensors only detect if a flame is present or not for flames in the UV and optical spectrum

Addressed research question:

- Limits of detection of current optical flame sensors for the blends with O₂
- Combination of acoustic and optical sensors to detect onset of dynamic instabilities

Fig 2. Schematic of experimental setup

Method:

- Flame tests with and without external excitation and subsequent analysis of the transient raw sensor signals with Python code
- Correlation of digital sensor data with kinetic simulations and chemiluminescent imaging provided by project partner GWA^[1]
- Combination of acoustic and optical sensor data for prediction of dynamic instability (s. Fig 3)
- Transfer of the above developed method on to industrially relevant combustors at a larger scale

Fig 3. Example of comparison between acoustic and UV normed sensor signal during flame blowout – indicated by sharp decrease in signal intensity; Results from IGF Project SeEWO of (OWI, GWA)

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